

UHMWPE FIBER SURFACE MODIFICATION BY ATOMIC LAYER DEPOSITION OF ALUMINA

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Abstract

Ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibers are highly crystalline fibers with superior mechanical properties and very high tensile strength. However, due to the fibers' non polar nature it is hard to bond them to other polymers. In this research, the fiber surface was modified using atomic layer deposition (ALD) of alumina at low temperatures. The surface treatment was aimed at increasing the adhesion between the fibers and an epoxy matrix without degrading the fiber mechanical properties (as often happens after fiber surface treatment).

The Microbond technique was used to quantify the interfacial shear strength between the UHMWPE fibers and the epoxy matrix and it was found to be tripled compared to a non-treated fiber, without reducing the fibers' ultimate tensile strength.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) were used to characterize chemical composition and surface morphology of the deposited layer. Young modulus and nano-hardness were derived from the nano-indentation measurements using an AFM probe. Nano-indentation results showed an order of magnitude increase in the fibers' Young modulus and nano-hardness after alumina deposition.

1 Introduction

The interface between a fiber and its surrounding matrix plays a crucial role in the mechanical behavior of a composite. UHMWPE fibers are highly crystalline fibers with very high tensile strength (3.9 GPa) [1]. The fibers are comprised of a large number of fibrils with a high degree of chain alignment, which gives the fibers their unusual strength. However, these fibers have poor adhesion to the different matrices they are intended to reinforce due to their non-polar surface. In order to improve their interfacial adhesion, the surface of the fibers must be treated before they are embedded in the matrix. Currently used surface treatments include: corona discharge [2], chemical treatments with chromic acid, potassium permanganate and hydrogen peroxide [3, 4], and different plasma treatments [5, 6], which are successful in enhancing the bonding between UHMWPE fibers and an epoxy matrix. These treatments increase the interfacial adhesion by removing any contaminants from the fiber surface as well as introducing roughness and/or polar functional groups on the surface of the fiber. These common surface treatments, however, degrade the UHMWPE fiber tensile strength by about 10% [3, 7].

The work presented herein suggests an alternative, new, method to improve fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion by adding a buffer inorganic ceramic layer

of aluminum oxide using atomic layer deposition (ALD). ALD is a vapor deposition technique based on two complementary self-limiting chemical reactions that take place sequentially and in an alternating fashion. The substrate is exposed alternately to each of the two precursors and by repeating this 2-step cycle a thin film is built up, one monolayer at a time to a desired well-defined thickness [8]. The ALD process can be used to coat both flat and high-aspect-ratio structures.

Thin layers of aluminum oxide were deposited by ALD, using H₂O and trimethylaluminum (TMA) as sources for oxygen and aluminum respectively. The ALD process was performed by alternately supplying pulses of argon flow gas containing either H₂O or TMA vapor according to the following two step process [8, 9]:

where the asterisks denote the surface species. Mechanical properties and chemical composition of the alumina coated fibers, as well as the interfacial shear strength between the fibers and epoxy matrix were studied.

2 Experimental

The study was carried out on single fiber/matrix micro-composites. The matrix was epoxy resin (Epusil EP-502, Polymer Gvulot, mixed with hardener EPC-9 at a ratio of 100:16). The fibers were Spectra 1000 - ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fiber (nominal diameter 27 μm) [10]. Single fiber/matrix samples were cured for 5 h at 80°C in air.

ALD (Fiji F200 system, Cambridge NanoTech at BIU) was employed for depositing aluminum oxide thin film coatings on UHMWPE fibers. The ALD was equipped with a remote plasma generator. Trimethylaluminum (TMA, Al(CH₃)₃) (Sigma-Aldrich) and water (18 MΩ) were used as precursors, without heating. Argon gas flowed continuously at a 260 sccm flow rate. The base

pressure was 0.16 Torr and the chamber temperature was set to 80°C. For some of the fibers, prior to the Al₂O₃ ALD process, the plasma generator (13.56 MHz) was activated for 1 min at 300 W, with an oxygen flow of 30 sccm and an argon flow of 200 sccm. This pretreatment (subsequently referred to as 1 min plasma) was used to increase the surface reactivity. Each ALD cycle consisted of a 0.06 s pulse of TMA, followed by a 15 s purge, and a 0.06 s pulse of water, followed by a 30 s purge.

Five different kinds of specimens were evaluated:

- (i) pristine UHMWPE fibers;
- (ii) 1 min plasma treated UHMWPE fibers;
- (iii) fibers coated by 23 nm alumina ALD without plasma pretreatment;
- (iv) 1 min plasma treated fibers followed by 7 nm alumina ALD;
- (v) 1 min plasma treated fibers followed by 23 nm alumina ALD.

7 nm alumina ALD and 23 nm alumina ALD were achieved after 100 and 350 coating cycles, respectively. The thickness of the deposited films was assessed by ellipsometric measurements of alumina deposited on a Si witness sample.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements of the alumina coating on flat UHMWPE samples were performed in a ultra-high vacuum (UHV) chamber (base pressure $\sim 4 \times 10^{-10}$ Torr) equipped with a non-monochromatic Al K_α X-ray radiation source operated at 1486.6 eV and a CLAM 2 hemispherical energy analyzer (VG Microtech). The spectrometer was calibrated to the position of the 3d_{5/2} line of clean-sputtered Ag of 368.25 eV binding energy [11]. A high sensitivity XPS scan was recorded in the 0–1200 eV energy range using a pass energy of 100 eV, while 20 eV pass energy was used for high resolution measurements of Al 2p, C 1s, and O 1s core level lines. Binding energies in the spectra have been corrected based on the position of adventitious carbon at 285.0 eV. The curve fitting of the core-

level XPS lines was carried out using the CasaXPS software with a Gaussian–Lorentzian product function and a non-linear Shirley background subtraction. A Gaussian/Lorentzian mixing ratio (GL) was taken as 0.3 for all lines. For quantitative estimations of surface compositions, standard atomic photo-ionization cross-section values from the SPECS data base were used [12].

The fibers' tensile strength was measured using a tensile testing system (Instron, Model 4502, 10 N load cell and strain rate 1 mm/min) [7].

An atomic force microscope (AFM) (Veeco, Multimode NanoScope) operating under ambient atmospheric conditions was utilized for the determination of surface roughness, as well as nano-mechanical properties of the coating (hardness and elastic modulus were derived from nano-indentation measurements using a diamond pyramid tip).

Microbond tests were carried out to measure the effect of alumina coatings on the fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength. The interfacial shear strength of single fiber/matrix samples was measured using an Instron. Fig. 1 illustrates the microbond technique including an image of an epoxy drop on an UHMWPE fiber. Fig. 2 shows a typical load-displacement curve obtained for UHMWPE/epoxy sample.

Fig. 1. Microbond method illustration (a) and optical microscope image of a drop on UHMWPE fiber (b).

Fig. 2. Microbond method typical load-displacement curve obtained for UHMWPE/epoxy sample.

Measurements of the dimensions of the epoxy droplets on the fiber were carried out using an optical microscope. The interfacial shear strength for each drop was calculated by dividing the load at failure by the contact area (πLD , where L is the embedded length and D is the fiber diameter). The results were averaged over 15 measurements.

3 Results and discussion

Aluminum oxide was deposited on UHMWPE fibers using ALD. Different samples, with different surface treatments were examined, including pristine fibers, fibers exposed to 1 minute plasma prior to aluminum oxide ALD treatment, fibers exposed to 1 minute plasma only, fibers exposed to aluminum oxide ALD treatment only. The adhesion of these variously treated fibers to an epoxy matrix was measured.

3.1 XPS studies

XPS analysis was carried out in order to evaluate the chemical composition of the ALD coating. Due to small dimensions of the fibers, the XPS measurements were performed on a flat, $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ UHMWPE (Dyneema) plate. UHMWPE plate was coated by 23 nm alumina ALD concurrently with the

fibers coating (sample type (v) in Experimental section).

Surface elemental composition derived from the XPS data are shown in Table 1. XPS analysis shows a substantial concentration of carbon on the surface. This carbon may originate either from “adventitious” contamination or from the underlying UHMWPE substrate. Another possibility is the presence of an unreacted TMA residue in the deposited layer. The quantitative analysis shows that the Al:O ratio is close to 2:3, indicating the existence of a stoichiometric Al₂O₃ oxide layer. The estimated thickness of this layer (23 nm) is higher than the XPS sampling depth (about 10 nm). Thus, it is suggested that the origin of the C1s peak is an “adventitious” contamination layer.

Table 1. Surface elemental composition (at. %) of 23 nm alumina ALD coated UHMWPE plate, derived from XPS data.

Peak	Assignment	Peak Position (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Atomic Conc. (%)
C 1s	C-C, C-H	285.0	2.0	27.3
C 1s	C=O	286.7	2.3	2.7
C 1s	-COH, -COOH	289.3	2.3	3.4
O 1s	Al-O	531.4	2.7	35.2
O 1s	C=O;-COH -COOH	532.8	2.7	7.5
Al 2p	Al-O	74.9	2.1	23.8

3.2 Fiber Tensile Strength

Fiber tensile strength and fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion were measured and the results are summarized in Table 2. The tensile strengths of UHMWPE fibers were measured after different surface treatments. These tests were used to build a tensile strength distribution curve based on over 22

measurements. The tensile strength distributions for each of the fibers after different treatments were analyzed using a Weibull model, as follows [13, 14]:

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right] \quad (1)$$

where $F(x)$ is the probability of failure up to the applied stress x ; β is the shape parameter that characterizes the width of the distribution; and α is the scale parameter, which is approximately the mean or the expected failure stress. The α and β parameters are presented in Table 2. The results show that UHMWPE tensile strength was not changed by the alumina coating.

It is known that a typical plasma treatment of 10-15 min can reduce fiber tensile strength by about 10% [3, 7]. In this study, the fibers were pre-treated by 1 min plasma before Al₂O₃ ALD; this might affect the fiber tensile strength in comparison to the non-treated Al₂O₃ ALD fibers. The plasma treatment conditions, such as plasma composition, pressure, treatment time, and plasma power, contribute to the final properties of the fiber surface. Short plasma treatment (of a few seconds) achieves some amount of surface oxidation, while longer treatment times might lead to both surface oxidation and cross-linking. This might increase the cohesive strength of the surface. A prolonged plasma exposure results in surface pitting that can lead to mechanical interlocking [14]. The mechanical interlocking further improves the interfacial adhesion, but causes a reduction in the fiber mechanical strength properties. For example, 2 hr of oxygen RF plasma exposure increases the surface roughness but reduces the fiber tensile strength by 50% [1, 15].

3.3 Interfacial Shear Strength

The microbond test results (see Table 2) show that the interfacial shear strength between the untreated UHMWPE fiber and the epoxy matrix is relatively

low (3.7 ± 0.5 MPa). However, the deposition of alumina (at thicknesses of 7 nm and 23 nm) on the plasma pretreated fibers increased the interfacial shear strength to 8.7 ± 1.5 MPa and 10.9 ± 3.8 MPa, respectively. The improvement in the interfacial adhesion with increasing alumina ALD thickness, along with the fact that increasing the ALD treatment time (more cycles) did not damage the fiber tensile strength, should be studied further by changing the alumina ALD thickness to 50 or 100 nm.

It should be noted that 1 min of plasma pretreatment without alumina coating also increases the interfacial adhesion (the interfacial shear strength of 8.9 ± 2.5 MPa). Thus, there is no need for the longer plasma treatment of 10-15 min, which compromises the fiber tensile strength.

The 1 min plasma treatment should be compared to the 23 nm alumina ALD coating without plasma pretreatment. It was found that the interfacial shear strength for both samples was quite similar, 8.9 ± 2.5 MPa and 8.5 ± 2.2 MPa, respectively. These results show that there is no need for plasma pretreatment in order to create a better interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix.

The 1 min plasma treated fibers followed by 23 nm alumina ALD coating was found to be the most effective treatment. Both high interfacial shear strength (10.9 MPa compared to 3.7 MPa for pristine fibers) and slight improvement in the fiber Weibull distribution shape parameter (8.1 in comparison to 6.3) were observed. Further examination with AFM demonstrates that the 23 nm alumina ALD coating resulted in higher surface roughness. Probably, the interfacial adhesion was improved by the combination of increased roughness and fiber functionalization, i.e. the addition of polar groups and the creation of a chemical bond, which is most important in polyolefin fiber/matrix adhesion mechanism [5, 7, 13].

The alumina ceramic coating may modify thermal stability of the composite in the same manner as the addition of clays and other nano-oxides to polymers

[16]. This hypothesis will be investigated in future work.

Table 2. The averaged interfacial shear strength and Weibull parameters (α - scale parameter in GPa and β - shape parameter) for the tested fiber/matrix microbond specimens and the tested fibers, respectively, after different surface treatments.

Fiber characteristics	Averaged interfacial shear strength (MPa)	α - scale parameter (GPa)	β - shape parameter (dimensionless)
Pristine UHMWPE fibers	3.7 ± 0.5	3.9	6.3
1 min plasma	8.9 ± 2.5	3.8	6.4
23 nm Al ₂ O ₃ ALD without plasma	8.5 ± 2.2	3.9	7.4
1 min plasma & 7 nm Al ₂ O ₃ ALD	8.7 ± 1.5	-	-
1 min plasma & 23 nm Al ₂ O ₃ ALD	10.9 ± 3.8	3.9	8.1

3.4 AFM studies and nano-indentation

UHMWPE fiber morphology was studied and the fibers surface roughness was measured to evaluate its contribution to the interfacial adhesion. The AFM results presented in Fig. 3 show that the surface roughness for the fibers that were coated by aluminum oxide ALD is higher ($R_q \sim 350$ nm) than the surface roughness of the pristine fibers ($R_q \sim 70$ nm). However, 1 min plasma treatment reduced the surface roughness of the fiber to $R_q \sim 40$ nm. Thus, it is believed that the enhancement of the interfacial

shear strength is not only surface roughness dependent, but is related also to surface activation by plasma treatment.

Fig. 3. AFM images of pristine UHMWPE fiber (a), UHMWPE fiber after 1 min plasma (b), and UHMWPE fiber after 1 min plasma treatment and 23 nm Al₂O₃ coating (c).

Nano-indentation tests by AFM were carried out in order to measure Young's modulus and hardness.

These mechanical properties are obtained from nanoindentation using loading and unloading cycles that generating force-displacement curves. The most common method for deriving the modulus, E , from loading-unloading curves is the Oliver-Pharr data analysis procedure [17]. The modulus is calculated using the following procedure. The stiffness S is calculated from the slope of the initial unloading and is define as

$$S = \frac{dP}{dh} \quad (2)$$

where P is the load and h is the displacement, as shown in Fig. 4. The load P is calculated by

$$P = \frac{4\mu A}{1-\nu} h \quad (3)$$

where μ is the shear modulus, A is the is contact area, and ν is the Poisson ratio.

The shear modulus can be related to the elastic modulus, E by

$$E = 2\mu(1 + \nu) \quad (4)$$

Thus, differentiating P with respect to h leads to

$$\frac{dP}{dh} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{A} \frac{E}{(1-\nu^2)} \quad (5)$$

The contact area, A , can be measured directly from the indent left on the surface. However, in the case of elastic materials or in cases in which there is no clear indent, the area is calculated by using the relation described in Eq. 6 which is used for the Berkovich tip (as is the case in this study)

$$A = 24.5h_c^2 \quad (6)$$

where h_c is the contact depth. h_c is derived from the relation $h_c = h_{max} - h_s$ where h_{max} is the maximum penetration depth and h_s can be determined from the load-penetration data, $h_s = \varepsilon P_{max}/S$, where ε is varied with indenter geometry (0.73 for Berkovich tip).

Integration of Eqs. 2, 5 and 6 yields the modulus:

$$E = S \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(1-\nu^2)}{2\sqrt{24.5h_c^2}} \quad (7)$$

The hardness, H , is defined as the load carried per projected area of the material during an indentation

process and it is calculated by

$$H = \frac{P}{A} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4. Typical Nanoindentation force (load) - displacement curve.

Fig. 5. Young's modulus of pristine UHMWPE fibers (black squares) and 23 nm alumina ALD coating on UHMWPE fibers (red triangles) under similar applied loads.

Figures 5 and 6 show that both the Young's modulus and the hardness of the fibers coated by 23 nm

alumina ALD layer increased by an order of magnitude in comparison to untreated fiber. The Young modulus was ~280 MPa after ALD coating, compared to 39 MPa for pristine fiber. The obtained hardness increased from 4.8 MPa for the pristine fiber to ~86 MPa for the 23 nm alumina ALD coated fibers. It should be noted the UHMWPE fiber modulus is the transverse strength. The increase in the coated fiber modulus is an indication that the fibers are indeed coated by alumina. It is, however, *not* the modulus of the alumina coating. The AFM tip depth penetration depends on the applied load and is within the range of 50-150 nm. Since the alumina coating thickness is estimated as 23 nm, the measured modulus, although increased, is affected by the fiber's lower strength. Further measurements should be carried out to evaluate the ALD alumina coating properties.

Fig. 6. The hardness of pristine UHMWPE fibers (black squares) and 23 nm alumina ALD coating on UHMWPE fibers (red triangles) under similar applied loads.

Conclusions

Alumina ALD coating of UHMWPE fibers was found to be effective in improving interfacial adhesion between UHMWPE fibers and an epoxy matrix without undermining the fibers' tensile strength. Pretreatment of 1 min in RF plasma was

found to be a sufficient exposure time to achieve improved interfacial shear adhesion without damaging the fiber mechanical properties. This must be compared to what is now the more widespread approach of 10-15 min plasma treatment, which increases the interfacial adhesion, but results in a reduction of the fiber tensile strength by about 10%. Increasing the thickness of the alumina ALD coating from 7 nm to 23 nm increased the interfacial adhesion without degrading the fiber mechanical properties.

XPS measurements indicated that the ALD layer has a stoichiometry of Al₂O₃. The ceramic coating improves both the fiber Young's modulus and the fiber hardness by at least order of magnitude (as is indicated by the nanoindentation measurements).

Further studies will be conducted in order to understand the mechanism of alumina deposition on the non-polar UHMWPE fiber. The studies will concentrate on the nature of the fiber-ALD layer bonding, as well as the mechanism of the interfacial adhesion improvement.

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